

Results of the WRC-23 regarding the 6GHz band...Good news or bad news?

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About me

Electronic Engineer (1993), with a Master on Technology Management (1999), both from Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana in Medellín. Obtained his PhD in Telecommunications from Universitat Politècnica de Valencia in 2003. IEEE member since 1995 and Senior Member since 2014. Advisor of the Spectrum Management Committee for Colombian Spectrum Agency and ITU expert. Former IEEE Comsoc LATAM Regional Director (2022-2023), Comsoc IT committee member. As ITU expert, advised different governments in Digital TV and Spectrum Management. Is a participant on COST CA 20120 INTERACT and former actions COST CA15104 IRACON, COST IC1004 and COST 2100

UNIVERSIDAD ICESI A OTRO NIVEL

Where I come
from?

- Cali is the third city in Colombia, and the main in the southwest.

About Universidad Icesi

- Icesi is a small private University located in Cali, founded by regional companies.
 - <http://www.icesi.edu.co>

ABET just reaccredited our Telematics Engineering, Industrial Engineering and Software Engineering programs, and for the first time the Bioquimical Engineering program.

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Roadmap for CTU

- The IEEE International Network Generations Roadmap (INGR) is a 900+ page technical document on future networks and wireless communications over 3-, 5-, and 10-year horizons.
- A chapter of the document is dedicated to Connecting the Unconnected, investigating how future generations of mobile systems will need to include standard access for all.
- Read the CTU chapter and others at:
<https://FutureNetworks.ieee.org/roadmap>

Outline

- About the 6GHz for WiFi 6E or IMT
- Some comments about World Radio Conferences and WRC-23
- WRC-23
- Las bandas de 6GHz y 10GHz para conectar los desconectados
- A final comment about NGSO or LEO (Low Earth Orbit)

6GHz for WiFi 6E

6GHz band for WiFi

- In 2020 the FCC issued regulation regarding the unlicensed use of the 6 GHz band, under the U-NII concept.
- The band is located between 5925 MHz to 6425 MHz and 6425 MHz to 7125MHz.
- A maximum power of 30dBm is allowed, plus antenna gain of 6dBi (EIRP 36 dBm), using a frequency coordination system - AFC.

6GHz band for WiFi

Band	Allowed Unlicensed Usage	Incumbents
UNII-5	Low Power Indoor	Fixed Service, Satellite Service
UNII-6	Low Power Indoor, Standard Power AP	Satellite Service, TV and Broadcast Services
UNII-7	Low Power Indoor	Fixed Service, Satellite Service
UNII-8	Low Power Indoor, Standard Power AP	Satellite Service, TV and Broadcast Services

FCC Allocation

<https://blogs.arubanetworks.com/corporate/the-6-ghz-band-say-goodbye-to-the-stone-age-of-wi-fi/>

Distribución en la UE

24 x 20 MHz
 12 x 40 MHz
 6 x 80 MHz
 3 x 160 MHz

<https://blogs.arubanetworks.com/corporate/the-6-ghz-band-say-goodbye-to-the-stone-age-of-wi-fi/>

- Adopted 5925-6425 MHz
- Adopted 5925-7125 MHz
- Adopted 5925-6425 MHz, Considering 6425-7125 MHz
- Considering 5925-6425 MHz

Worldwide adoption (before WRC-23)

Why the importance of 6 GHz band for IMT

- 6GHz is considered a medium-high band
- Better coverage than millimeter waves (26 GHz and up) , more capacity than low and mid bands.
- MIMO Works well in this band, as well as other new technologies like RIS.
- For Small ISP in point to point and Point to Multipoint is very interesting.

Current IMT bands

ITU allocates spectrum for IMT at World Radiocommunication Conferences (WRCs)

WRC-19 identified **17.25 GHz of spectrum** for IMT in 5 bands. **86%** of these bands are harmonized .

https://www.itu.int/wrs-22/wp-content/uploads/sites/25/2022/10/IMT_general_aspects_WRS-22-2.pdf

FR1 bands

- Under 6GHz
- Between 410MHz until 3700 or 3800 MHz
 - 410MHz
 - 450 - 470MHz
 - 700MHz
 - 850MHz
 - 900MHz
 - 1900MHz
 - 1800 MHz (O DCS)
 - AWS-3 (2100 pareado con 1700)
 - 2500MHz
 - 3500MHz

FR2 or millimeter wave bands

NR Operating Band	FR2 Bands				Duplex Mode	NR Bandwidths	Nickname(s)
	Uplink (UL) operating band Base Station (BS) receive User Equipment (UE) transmit		Downlink (DL) operating band Base Station (BS) transmit User Equipment (UE) receive				
	FDL_Low	FDL_High	FDL_Low	FDL_High			
n257	26.5 GHz	29.5 GHz	26.5 GHz	29.5 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	28 GHz Band
n258	24.25 GHz	27.5 GHz	24.25 GHz	27.5 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	26 GHz Band
n259	39.50 GHz	43.50 GHz	39.50 GHz	43.50 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	41 GHz Band
n260	37 GHz	40 GHz	37 GHz	40 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	39 GHz Band
n261	27.5 GHz	28.35 GHz	27.5 GHz	28.35 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	28 GHz Band
n262	47.20 GHz	48.20 GHz	47.20 GHz	48.20 GHz	TDD	50, 100, 200, 400	47 GHz Band
n263	57.0 GHz	71.0 GHz	57.0 GHz	71.0 GHz	TDD	100, 400, 800, 1600, 2000	60 GHz Band

Spectrum for IMT at WRC-23

WRC-23 will consider 7 candidate bands for IMT - UHF band and mid-band frequency ranges

About WRC-23 outcomes

WRC-23

5 570-6 700 MHz

Allocation to services		
Region 1	Region 2	Region 3
5 925-6 700	FIXED 5.457 FIXED-SATELLITE (Earth-to-space) 5.457A 5.457B MOBILE 5.457C ADD 5.6A12 ADD 5.6B12 ADD 5.6C12 5.149 5.440 5.458	

Region 1 and 3

5.6A12 The frequency bands 6 425-7 125 MHz in Region 1 and 7 025-7 125 MHz in Region 3 are identified for use by administrations wishing to implement the terrestrial component of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT). This identification does not preclude the use of these frequency bands by any application of the services to which they are allocated and does not establish priority in the Radio Regulations. Resolution [COM4/7] (WRC-23) applies.

The frequency bands are also used for the implementation of wireless access systems (WAS), including radio local area networks (RLANs). (WRC-23)

Region 3

5.6B12 In Cambodia, Lao P.D.R. and the Maldives, the frequency band 6 425-7 025 MHz is identified for the terrestrial component of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT). This identification does not preclude the use of this frequency band by any application of the services to which it is allocated and does not establish priority in the Radio Regulations. Resolution [COM4/7] (WRC-23) applies. (WRC-23)

Region 2

5.6C12 In Brazil and Mexico, the frequency band 6 425-7 125 MHz is identified for the terrestrial component of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT). The use of this frequency band for the implementation of IMT is subject to seeking agreement under No. **9.21** with neighbouring countries. This identification does not preclude the use of this frequency band by any application of the services to which it is allocated and does not establish priority in the Radio Regulations. Resolution [**COM4/7**] (**WRC-23**) applies.

The frequency band is also used for the implementation of wireless access systems (WAS), including radio local area networks (RLANs). (WRC-23)

6GHz Band WRC-23 results

Good News or bad News?

WiFi Now

- **Our take: Wi-Fi industry scores important 6 GHz victory at WRC-23. The rest is now up to us.**

IMT visions

- The World Radiocommunication Conference 2023 (WRC-23) concluded with groundbreaking spectrum decisions that will shape the future of mobile communications. Governments agreed on new mobile low-band spectrum (below 1 GHz) and mid-band spectrum in the 3.5 GHz and 6 GHz ranges. ([Vapps Group](#))
- MY LATEST (Mike Dano)
An international gathering of spectrum policymakers announced decisions on several hot topics, including opening a portion of the 6GHz band for 5G.
The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) made the move at its quadrennial World Radiocommunication Conference (WRC-23), which started last month in Dubai, United Arab Emirates (UAE) and ended today. It is intended to harmonize spectrum usage across the world so that operators, equipment vendors and others can avoid international fragmentation and leverage global economies of scale.
The [GSMA](#) trade group cheered the WRC-23 decision to set aside 6.425-7.125GHz for licensed, mobile operations.
"The 6GHz band is the only remaining midband spectrum currently available to respond to the data traffic growth in the 5G-Advanced era," GSMA said in a statement.

To conclude

- All involved parts are satisfied and at the same time dissatisfied because of the results.
- However, there are available Technologies to use the 6 GHz band to improve connectivity and connect the unconnected.

A final comment about NGSO or LEO (Low Earth Orbit)

LEO

NGSO is technically a Good alternative, but its prices are not affordable by the half of the humanity still unconnected.

Additional work is needed and innovative ideas are necessary.

